

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ENGINEERING AND APPLIED TECHNOLOGY

ABOUT IJEAT

International Journal Engineering and Applied Technology (IJEAT) will be launched at the Nusa Putra University, Sukabumi, Indonesia in 2018. The first paper will be published in March 2018 with a frequency of two issues per year (May and November).

IJEAT will publish two volumes per year. In order to accelerate and streamline the manuscript handling process, an online manuscript submission system, together with the website of IJEAT will be set up in 2018. After the launch, this journal may provide open access to its contents in the near future on the principle that making research findings freely available to the public supports a greater global exchange of knowledge, which in turn can enhance the usefulness and visibility of IJEAT.

Now, the IJEAT Secretariat and the Editorial Office of the IJEAT have been transferred from STT Nusa Putra to Nusa Putra University, Sukabumi, Indonesia. Agustami Sitorus, Lecturer in Department of Mechanical Engineering Nusa Putra University, is currently serving as the Editor-in-Chief of IJEAT. At present, all the manuscripts and other correspondence should be directed to the Editorial Office of IJEAT at the address given below.

IJEAT Editorial Office

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AIMS & SCOPE

IJEAT publishes original papers only and the submission of a manuscript will be taken to imply that the contributions are original and that no similar manuscript has been or is being submitted to other journals. Manuscripts are solicited from all areas of specialization in engineering. IJEAT is an international

and multidisciplinary journal. The major goal of the journal is to communicate advances in engineering and applied technology, with a particular preference to Asia, to researchers, practicing engineers and decision makers of developing countries. IJEAT publishes peer-reviewed research papers (both theoretical and applied) and state-of-the-art reviews related to Engineering and technology. The scope of the journal includes mechanical engineering, civil engineering, industrial engineering, electrical engineering, power engineering, environmental engineering, postharvest technology, food technology, biotechnology and emerging technologies. Subjects of basic engineering and science such as instrumentation, machinery design, human factor and ergonomics, global warming, renewable energy, climate change, terramechanics and new materials are also included in the scope of IJEAT.

MILESTONE IJEAT

Figure 1 Milestone development of IJEAT

AUTHOR'S GUIDELINE

The International Journal Engineering and Applied Technology (IJEAT) publishes original papers only and submission of a manuscript will be taken to imply that the material is original and that no similar paper has been or is being submitted elsewhere. In technically categories the journal not only on engineering and technology but also in can be in another subjects of basic engineering and science such as instrumentation, machinery design, human factor and ergonomics, global warming, renewable energy, climate change, terramechanics and new materials. The journal receives three types of papers: research papers, research notes and review papers.

Submission: The manuscripts must be submitted as an MS Word file (see template). It's must be written in English on A4 size paper (210 mm × 297 mm) in 1.5 spacing with with each every margin on top, bottom and right are 3.0 cm and 4 cm margin in left. Manuscripts should be single spaced and submitted in "Lucida Fax", 10.5 point font. Pages should be numbered in the bottom right corner. All figures, diagrams, drawings, photographs, and tables inserted in the end of the text. The length of the manuscript should not more than 10,000 words or 20 printed pages inclusive of figures and tables. Complete email addresses should be included in the manuscripts on the first page. The electronic manuscripts file should be sent by email to Ijeatnusaputra@gmail.com.

Manuscript Style & Format. It is highly recommended that authors review several papers published in IJEAT to become familiar with the style and format. The English composition quality must be acceptable for publication in a quality international journal. If the English quality is unacceptable, manuscripts will be returned to the authors. These guidelines for authors must be followed precisely and rigidly. Failure to do so will result in manuscripts being returned to authors and consequent delay of the peer review process.

Title, Authors and affiliations. The title should supply enough information for the reader to make a reliable decision on probable interest. A short informative title is preferred over a long obtuse one. Titles should not more

than 20 words, except in unusual instances. A good title should identify (briefly) the subject, indicate the purpose of the subject and contain keywords.

Provide the first names or initials (if used), middle names or initials (if used), surnames, and affiliations, including department, university or organization, city, state/province and country for all authors. One of the authors should be designated as the corresponding author, whose email address should also be provided.

Use “Lucida Fax”, 14 point bold font for the title only, use 10.5 point font for remainder of manuscript. Title must be using “small caps”. Put complete email addresses below the title and affiliations on the first page.

Abstract. The purpose of an abstract is to provide a clear and concise summary of the information that has been presented in an article. Each paper must have an abstract not more than 350 words, between the title and the beginning of the paper. The abstract should state briefly the purpose of the research, the principal results and major conclusions. Literature citations and references such as tables, figures or equations that have been found in the body of the manuscript should not be used in abstract. It’s means, when the researchers prepare an abstract, they should think about “this is what we studied”, “This is how we did it”, “This is what we learned” and “This is what it means”.

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Introduction. The introduction should include a brief statement of why the research was conducted. The problem, present objectives, including a description of the subject, scope, and purpose along with a plan of development of the subject matter should also be included. The introduction's purpose is to encourage the reader to read further.

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protocol so that other scientists could reproduce the experiments. You should reference all methods previously used and specify whether the methods had been modified and, if so, how.

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The data are interpreted in the discussion section. A correlation with previous findings should be made by identifying how and why there are differences and where there is agreement. Speculation is encouraged but it must be identified. The discussion should present the major results and interpretations of the work including some explanation on the significance of these conclusions. Controversy should also be presented clearly and fairly.

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Acknowledgements. Acknowledgments will appear at the end of the printed article and should run no more than approximately five sentences in length.

References. At the end of the text, there should be a section headed "References". The full references should be quoted in alphabetical order using the first author's surname with Arabic numbers. Each reference includes the names of all the authors, year, the title in the original language (and translation, where available), source, volume, issue number (in parentheses) and page numbers, in that order. Ensure that every reference cited in the text is also present in the reference list (and vice versa). Unpublished results and personal communications are not recommended in the reference list, but may be mentioned in the text. References should be arranged first alphabetically and then further sorted

chronologically if necessary. More than one reference from the same author(s) in the same year must be identified by the letters “a”, “b”, “c”, etc., placed after the year of publication.

Reference samples:

Ginting M., Nouari N., Lebaal. 2009. A Study of Surface Integrity when Machining Refractory Titanium Alloys. *Journal Advanced Materials Research*. 83(1): 83-86.

Groover P., Mikel. 1996. *Fundamentals of Modern Manufacturing Materials. Processes and Systems*. John Wiley & Sons Inc. New York.

Ranganathan T., Senthilvelan. 2011. Multi-response optimization of machining parameters in hot turning using grey analysis. *Journal springerlink*. 56(1): 455-462.

Z. Pan, S.Y. Liang. 2017. Material driven machining process modeling. *Journal Manufacturing Letters*. 14(1): 1-5.

Pöhlitz J., Jan R., Barbara K., Steffen S., Hans-Jörg V. 2018. Computed tomography and soil physical measurements of compaction behaviour under strip tillage, mulch tillage and no tillage. *Soil & Tillage Research*. 175: 205-216.

Sitorus A., Wawan H., Radite P.A.S. 2017. Design and Performance of Combine Corn Transplanter Powered by Hand Tractor. In: *Proceedings from 3rd International Conference on Computing Engineering and Design (ICCED)*, Malaysia, November 23-25, 2017: 20-28.

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For new equations, state all assumptions and initial boundary conditions, and give sufficient derivation for the reader to understand the development. Show only those mathematical steps required for comprehension. Interpret the

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$$z = \frac{(ax+by)^2}{(cx+dy)} \quad (1)$$

Figures, Graphs, and Charts. Authors should include figures to emphasize points made in the text, not merely to illustrate tabular material graphically. Illustrations attract the reader's attention, clarify the text, and should not be included unless discussed in the text. Graphs and charts should be designed to improve the general presentation of a technical publication by reporting data in a manner easy to comprehend. The decision to select and use charts or graphs should be governed by the writer's message and the points to be brought out in the illustration. Graphs primarily show trends; therefore, it is not necessary for you to show all the coordinate rulings in most graphs.

For the most beneficial use of illustrations, please observe the following points:

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2. Figure titles are unnecessary. The title information should be contained in the figure caption in below Figures, Graphs, and Charts as "Figure 1 XXX".
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